

Synthesis of Substituted Indolylthiazolidinones and Indolylazetidiones

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Indoles¹ and 4-thiazolidinones² possess a wide spectrum of biological activities. The reactivity of β -lactam moiety is greatly influenced by substituents or fused rings^{3,4}. 2-Azetidinones also possess a variety of therapeutic activities^{4,5}. The present communication reports the synthesis of biheterocyclic derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones and 2-azetidiones. These compounds have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

2-Phenyl-3-aminoindole⁶ on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes yielded 2-phenyl-3-substituted-benzalaminoindoles (2). Compounds 2 on cyclocondensation with thioglycolic acid/thiolactic acid yielded the 4-thiazolidinones (3Tg-Tl) and with thiomalic acid in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride yielded 4-thiazolidinones (3TM). The four-membered β -lactam ring is introduced in 2 by the cycloaddition of chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine to yield 2-azetidiones (4) (Scheme 1).

Biological activities : Compounds 2 and 3 were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities by cup-plate method⁷ at concentration of 50 μ g using DMF as solvent. The activity was compared with known drugs. The zone of inhibition was measured in mm.

All the compounds showed moderate activities. However, some of the compounds exhibited significant activity comparable with known antibiotics. In case of antibacterial activity of compounds 2a-q, the derivatives when R = 2,4-dichlorophenyl (20 mm), 4-methoxyphenyl (21) and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-

Scheme 1

phenyl (20) showed comparable activities with ampicillin (22) and norfloxacin (21) against *S. aureus*. In case of compounds 3(Tg), the derivatives when R = 2-methoxyphenyl (20 mm) and 4-methoxyphenyl (22) were comparable with ampicillin (22) and norfloxacin (21) against *S. aureus* and the derivative R = 2-methoxyphenyl (20) showed comparable activity with chloramphenicol (21) against *E. coli*. In case of compounds 3(Tl), the derivative when R = 9-anthryl showed comparable activity with norfloxacin (21) and chloramphenicol (21) against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively. In case of compounds 3(Tm), the derivatives when R = 2,4-dichlorophenyl

(21 mm), 2-methoxyphenyl (21) and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (20) showed comparable activities with ampicillin (22) and norfloxacin (21) against *S. aureus*.

The 2-azetidinone compounds (4) having R = phenyl (20 mm) and 4-nitrophenyl (20) showed comparable activities with chloramphenicol (22) against *S. pyogenes*, and having R = 2-nitrophenyl (22 mm) and 4-hydroxyphenyl (20) exhibited comparable activities with chloramphenicol (22 and 21) against *K. arogens* and *E. coli* respectively.

The methoxy derivatives were found most active and its presence resulted in the increase of antibacterial activity. The compounds showed moderate antifungal activity which was not comparable to griseofulvin.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1 435-IR spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Hitachi R-1200 (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol-JMS D-300 spectrometer. The purity of compounds was routinely checked by tlc using silica gel G (Merck). Elemental analysis was carried out with a Coleman analyser.

2-Phenyl-3-p-methoxybenzalaminoindole (2k) : A mixture of 3-amino-2-phenylindole (0.01 mol) and 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting solid was washed with 30% sodium bisulphite solution, dried and crystallised from 1,4-dioxane-ethanol (95%) (3 : 1), yield 71%, m.p. 139° (Found : C, 80.91; H, 5.49; N, 8.61. $C_{22}H_{18}N_2O$ requires : C, 80.98; H, 5.52; N, 8.58%); ν_{max} 3 400 (NH), 3 080, 1 540, 1 420, 1 310, 830, (C=C-H, C=C aromatic + indole moiety), 1 340 (C-N), 1 240 (C-O-C asym.) 1 060 (C-O-C sym.) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C-N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.05 (1H, s, N=CH), 7.13-8.19 (12H, m, Ar-H), 9.12 (1H, s, NH-indole); m/z 326 (M^+ base peak), 325, 219, 193, 179, 135, 133 and 77.

Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

2-Aryl-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-5-H/methyl-4-thiazolidinones (3(Tg)h) : A mixture of 2k (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol) was heated at 115-120° for 12 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and triturated with 2N sodium bicarbonate and the resulting solid was washed with excess of water, dried and crystallised from methanol-water, yield 63%, m.p. 116° (Found : C, 71.8 ; H, 4.9, N, 6.99. $C_{24}H_{20}N_2O_2S$ requires : C, 72.0 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 7.0%); ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 3 000, 1 500, 1 460, 1 100 (=C-H + C=C aromatic + indole moiety), 1 330 (C-N), 2 950 (CH asym.), 2 880 (CH sym.), 1 220 (C-O-C asym.), 1 070 (C-O-C sym.), 1 660 (C=O), 1 020 (C-N) and 700 cm^{-1} (C-S-C); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO- d_6) 3.61 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.25 (1H, s, N-CH-R), 7.3-7.7 (13H, m, Ar-H), 9.5 (1H, s, NH-indole) and 11.94-12.1 (1H, s, OH enolic of 4-thiazolidinone).

Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2-4*

Sl no	R	X	M p °C
2d	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	—	218
2k	4-Methoxyphenyl	—	139
2m	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-phenyl	—	102
3(Tg)g	2-Methoxyphenyl	H	200
3(Tg)h	4-Methoxyphenyl	H	63
3(TI)k	4-Methoxyphenyl	CH ₃	195
3(TI)q	9-Anthryl	CH ₃	199
3(TM)d	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	CH ₂ COOH	360
3(TM)j	2-Methoxyphenyl	CH ₂ COOH	285
3(TM)k	4-Methoxyphenyl	CH ₂ COOH	299
3(TM)l	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	CH ₂ COOH	360
4a	phenyl	—	295
4i	4-Hydroxyphenyl	—	104
4k	4-Methoxyphenyl	—	107
4n	2-Nitrophenyl	—	238
4p	4-Nitrophenyl	—	245

* In all 68 compounds were prepared in 2-3 series including compounds where R = (a) phenyl, (b) 2-chlorophenyl, (c) 4-chlorophenyl, (d) 2,4-dichlorophenyl, (e) 2,6-dichlorophenyl, (f) 3,4-dichlorophenyl, (g) 2-hydroxyphenyl, (h) 3-hydroxyphenyl, (i) 4-hydroxyphenyl, (j) 2-methoxyphenyl, (k) 4-methoxyphenyl, (l) 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl, (m) 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl, (n) 2-nitrophenyl, (o) 3-nitrophenyl, (p) 4-nitrophenyl, (q) 9-anthryl. all compounds gave satisfactory N analysis

2-Aryl-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones (3(Tl)k): A mixture of **2k** (0.01 mol) and thiolactic acid (0.02 mol) was heated at 120° for 9–10 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and triturated by 2*N* sodium bicarbonate solution and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from 1,4-dioxan-ethanol, yield 63%, m.p. 95° (Found : C, 72.44; H, 5.28, N, 6.70. C₂₅H₂₂N₂O₂S requires : C, 72.46; H, 5.31; N, 6.76%); ν_{\max} 3350 (NH), 3100, 1610, 1250, 1100 (C=H, C=C aromatic + indole moiety), 1650 (C=O), 2820 (CH sym.), 1170 (C–N), 1240 (C–O–C asym.), 1025 (C–O–C sym.), 695 (C–S–C); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆), 1.4 (3H, d, CHCH₃), 2.60 (1H, q, CHCH₃), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.8–7.9 (13H, m, ArH), 7.8 (1H, s, N–CH–R), 9.5 (1H, s, NH-indole); *m/z* 414 (*M*⁺ base peak), 326, 313, 252, 219, 206, 191, 180, 165, 113 and 77.

Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

2-Aryl-3-(2'-phenylindole-3'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (3(TM)k): A mixture of **2k** (0.01 mol) and thiomalic acid (0.015 mol) in the presence of anhydrous ZnCl₂ (1.0 g) was condensed at 160° for 2 h and then the temperature was raised to 180° for 1 h. The product obtained was dissolved in 4*N* sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate was treated with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol-DMF (2 : 1), yield 60%, m.p. 299° (Found : C, 68.15; H, 4.78 ; N, 6.16. C₂₆H₂₂N₂O₄S requires : C, 68.12 ; H, 4.80, N, 6.11%); ν_{\max} 3350 (NH), 3100, 1610, 1225, 1165, 1100 (=CH + C=C aromatic + indole moiety), 3000 (CH asym.) 2950 (CH sym.), 1250 (C–O–C asym.), 1020 (C–O–C sym.) 1165 (C–N), 1665 (C=O), 1740 (C=O of acid) and 710 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C str.); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 3.61 (1H, s, OCH₃), 3.7 (2H, d, CHCHCOOH), 4.5 (1H, t, S-CHCH₂CO₂H), 6.81–7.92 (13H, m, ArH), 7.80 (1H, s, N–CH–R), 9.51 (1H, s, NH-indole), 11.5, 11.95–12.2 (1H, s, OH enolic of 4-thiazolidinone + CH₂COOH).

Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

4-Aryl-1-(2'-phenylindole-3'-yl)-3-chloro-2-azetidines (4k): To a stirred solution of **2k** (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dry 1,4-dioxane (50 ml) was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) dropwise at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h and kept for 2 days at room temperature. The precipitates of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered and washed with dioxane. The excess of solvent 1,4-dioxane was distilled off and the contents were poured on crushed ice. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from 99% ethanol, yield 67%, m.p. 107° (Found : C, 83.43 ; H, 4.75 ; N, 6.94. C₂₄H₁₉ClN₂O₂ requires : C, 83.47 ; H, 4.72; N, 6.96%); ν_{\max} 3400 (NH), 3090, 1600, 1160 (=CH + C=C aromatic + indole moiety), 1380 (C–N), 2950 (CH asym.), 2880 (CH sym.), 1220 (C–O–C asym.), 1025 (C–O–C sym.), 1720 (C=O) and 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ (CDCl₃) 3.66 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.3 (1H, d, ClCH.CH–R), 3.8 (1H, d, R–CH.CHCl), 6.8–7.6 (17H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, NH-indole); *m/z* 402.5, 326 (*M*⁺ base peak), 311, 281, 219, 163 and 77.

Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

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